

Assessment of MRI Geometric Distortion for Radiotherapy Planning

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Abstract

Geometric accuracy in magnetic resonance imaging is a critical factor in radiotherapy planning; however, MRI images are subject to distortions arising from the physical limitations of the method. This study proposes an accessible approach for assessing geometric distortion in an MRI scanner using two phantoms – a commercial anthropomorphic phantom STEEV and a custom-made phantom fabricated from ABS plastic. Computed tomography data were employed as the reference standard. The methodology is based on linear measurements of periodic structures in a DICOM viewer, followed by deviation calculations. The spatial nature of distortion and its dependence on the distance from the scanner isocenter are demonstrated. A relationship between the magnitude of distortions and target volume is established, upon which practical recommendations for incorporating distortion into planning target volume formation are formulated. The proposed approach and the custom-made phantom may be utilized for routine quality assurance in resource-limited clinical settings.

Introduction

Magnetic resonance imaging is widely employed in radiotherapy owing to its high soft-tissue contrast, which enables more precise visualization of tumor targets and critical structures. However, MRI possesses a significant limitation — the presence of geometric distortions, attributable to inhomogeneity of the static magnetic field, gradient field nonlinearity, chemical shift, and other physical effects.

For radiotherapy, particularly in stereotactic radiosurgery where high spatial precision is essential, even minor distortions may prove critical. Failure to account for distortion can result in systematic errors in target localization, thereby reducing treatment efficacy and increasing the risk of complications. Computed tomography, in contrast to MRI, exhibits minimal geometric distortions due to the rigid geometry of the X-ray tube and detectors; consequently, CT images may serve as a reference standard for assessing MRI distortion.

Aim of the study — to measure distortion on MR-images using two phantoms and to evaluate its impact on radiotherapy planning.

Research objectives:

1. Review of the scientific literature on MRI distortion.
2. Selection of a method for measuring distortions in head scanning.
3. Development and evaluation of a custom-made phantom from ABS plastic.
4. Scanning of the commercial STEEV phantom and the custom-made phantom on MRI and CT scanners.
5. Measurements of the acquired images.
6. Comparative analysis of MRI and CT images.
7. Assessment of distortion relative to reference CT data.
8. Quantitative evaluation of the impact of distortion on radiotherapy treatment plans.

Materials and methods

Phantoms

Two phantoms are employed in the study.

The first was a commercial anthropomorphic STEEV phantom (CIRS Inc., USA), simulating human body structures. A cubic insert measuring $63 \times 63 \times 93 \text{ mm}^3$ with periodic internal structures was utilized for measurements, enabling distortion assessment in the central region of the scanner.

The second phantom was designed and fabricated by the myself from ABS plastic (acrylonitrile butadiene styrene). Its overall dimensions are $143 \times 192 \times 95 \text{ mm}^3$, with periodic internal structures (rows of cubes) for tracking spatial distortions. The selection of ABS plastic was motivated by its financial availability, ease of machining, and high hydrogen proton content, which provides an adequate signal on MR images. This phantom is intended for distortion assessment across the entire field of view, including peripheral regions.

The combination of two phantoms of differing dimensions enables comprehensive distortion assessment: STEEV provides local measurements at the center, while the custom-made phantom provides global measurements across the entire field of view.

Fig.1 – anthropomorphic STEEV phantom (CT image)

Fig.2 – handmade phantom (ABS-plastic);
scanning machine: MRI Siemens MAGNETOM Aera,
CT Phillips Brilliance iCT
European Medical center (Moscow, RU);

Image Processing

Image processing was conducted in two stages: primary delineation in a DICOM viewer and subsequent statistical analysis in Microsoft Excel.

The processing sequence included:

1. Structure identification — periodic rows of structures (cubes) were visually identified on axial and sagittal MRI and CT slices for both the STEEV phantom and the custom-made ABS phantom.

Fig.3 – Axial MRI slice acquired on a Siemens MAGNETOM Aera system at 1.5 T
Scanning mode: T1-weighted imaging

Fig.4 - Axial CT slice of the custom-made ABS phantom acquired on a Philips Brilliance iCT system

2. Linear measurement — distances between corresponding control points (edges of structures) along the OX and OZ axes for each row were measured on both image types using the calibrated linear measurement tool integrated into the DICOM viewer. Measurements were performed for all available rows across the entire field of view.

Fig. 5,6 – linear measurements via DICOM viewer

3. Absolute distortion calculation — for each measured distance, the absolute difference between the values obtained on MRI and the reference CT was computed: $\Delta = |L_{\text{MRI}} - L_{\text{CT}}|$. Calculations were performed in Microsoft Excel.

4. Measurement error estimation — the accuracy of manual delineation in the DICOM viewer was taken as half the voxel size, corresponding to ± 0.05 mm. This value was adopted as the systematic measurement error.

5. Density profile analysis – to verify the identity of the measured structures and assess spatial correspondence, one-dimensional density profiles were constructed for both imaging modalities. For CT, the Hounsfield scale (measured in Hounsfield Units, HU) was used, which quantitatively reflects X-ray attenuation coefficients relative to water. For MRI, signal intensity (measured in arbitrary relative units) was used, reflecting proton density and T1 relaxation properties of the tissue. The profiles were plotted along the same spatial coordinates for corresponding CT and MRI slices.

For the STEEV phantom, the peaks on CT and MRI density profiles coincided, confirming accurate spatial correspondence between the two imaging modalities in the central region. For the custom-made ABS phantom, peaks on CT and MRI profiles were found to be mismatched at peripheral locations. This mismatch indicates the presence of systematic geometric distortion, since the same physical structure (the ABS plastic cube) is detected by both modalities but assigned to different

Fig.7 - Graph of the dependence of tissue density on the coordinate on MRI and CT (STEEV phantom)

Fig.8 - Graph of the dependence of tissue density on the coordinate on MRI and CT (ABS-plastic phantom)

6. Graph plotting — based on the obtained linear measurement data, graphs of distortion magnitude (Δ) versus distance from the scanner isocenter along the OX and OZ axes were plotted in Excel for both phantoms. These graphs demonstrated that for both phantoms, distortion was minimal in the central zone (within 30–50 mm from isocenter) and increased progressively toward the periphery. The custom-made ABS phantom, due to its larger dimensions, revealed more pronounced distortion at the edges of the field of view compared to the STEEV phantom, confirming the spatial dependence of geometric inaccuracies inherent to gradient nonlinearities.

7. Dose modeling — based on the obtained distortion values, a simulation of the impact of

geometric target shift on the D99% parameter (dose covering 99% of the PTV volume) was performed using an analytical model of target center displacement.

Measurements of ABS-plastic handmade phantom:

THE DEPENDENCE OF DISTORTION ON THE DISTANCE

Fig. 10. Graph of the dependence of the distortion of the MRI image along the OX axis on the distance to the central OZ axis in the axial slice

Fig. 11. Arrangement of rows of phantom structures

DEPENDENCE OF THE DISTORTION ON THE DISTANCE TO THE AXIS

Fig. 12. Distortion map on the axial slice of the phantom

Fig. 13. Axial slice of the phantom image

DEPENDENCE OF THE DISTORTION ON THE DISTANCE TO OY

Fig. 14. Graph of the dependence of the distortion of the MRI image along the OZ axis on the distance to the central OY axis in the sagittal section.

Fig. 15. The location of the axes in the image

DEPENDENCE OF THE DISTORTION ON THE DISTANCE TO THE AXIS

Fig. 16. Distortion map on the sagittal section of the phantom

Fig. 17. Sagittal slice of the phantom image

For the custom-made phantom, a clear spatial dependence of distortion was revealed, confirming the results obtained with STEEV but with greater amplitude at the periphery.

In the central zone (within 50 mm from isocenter), the mean distortion was 0.30 ± 0.05 mm.

At the periphery (beyond 50 mm from isocenter), deviations reached 1.50 ± 0.05 mm or more.

The maximum recorded values at the periphery were: in the axial plane, distortion reached 3.1

mm at a distance of 102 mm from the center; in the sagittal plane — 1.8 mm.

Measurements of anthropomorphic commercial STEEV phantom:

Fig.18,19 – dependence of distortion on coordinate; the sequence of rows inside STEEV phantom

Linear measurements of the periodic structures of the STEEV phantom revealed that in the central region of the scanner, discrepancies between MRI and CT are minimal. As distance from the isocenter increases, distortion growth was observed. The maximum absolute deviation of linear dimensions across all measured rows did not exceed 0.95 mm. In the central zone (within 30 mm from isocenter), distortions did not exceed 0.2 mm, confirming the high linearity of the gradient system near the magnet center.

Density profiles demonstrated coincidence of peaks on CT and MRI, confirming correct identification of structures by both methods.

Results

1. Graphs of distortion versus coordinate along the OX and OZ axes demonstrate a monotonic increase in distortions toward the edges of the field of view. Density profiles for peripheral structures showed a mismatch — commercial STEEV and custom-made ABS plastic – enabled distortion assessment both locally and across the entire field of view.
2. For the STEEV phantom, the maximum distortion did not exceed 0.95 mm, confirming high accuracy in the central zone.

3. For the custom-made phantom, distortions are minimal in the central zone (0.30 ± 0.05 mm), while at the periphery (> 50 mm) they reach 1.50 ± 0.05 mm or more. The maximum recorded values were 3.1 mm in the axial plane and 1.8 mm in the sagittal plane.
4. Distortion exhibits a pronounced spatial dependence: it increases with distance from the isocenter, which must be taken into account when planning irradiation of peripheral structures.
5. Distortion up to and including 1 mm is not critical for targets larger than 1.6 cm^3 ; distortion of 2 mm or greater is critical for targets smaller than 5.2 cm^3 . For small targets, distortions may have clinically significant consequences.
6. The combination of two phantoms enables distortion assessment both locally and across the entire field of view.
7. Routine distortion control is a mandatory condition for ensuring radiotherapy quality.
8. The obtained results are being implemented in clinical practice: when planning irradiation of metastases, the planning target volume margin is adjusted according to target localization and the magnitude of distortion in that region.

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